

Navigating through the New Terrain: Regional Dynamics and Nontraditional Security Threats in the Globalized Era

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Abstract

The terrain of security challenges are evolving with times. The following paper, tries to closely examine the changing paradigm of global security in the post-Cold War Globalized world. At present Nontraditional Security (NTS) threats can't be defined in an unidimensional way with wider possibilities from economic inequalities, human security threats, ideological extremities like Terrorism to environmental issues. The common characteristics of these threats are their transnational characteristics which is assuming priority over the conventional military threats. The analytical study have touched upon the historical foundations of such threats and the role of Bretton Woods institutions like WTO, IMF and World Bank in addressing the global issues. When comprehending such geostrategic and dynamic threats, the regional reactions and the conflicts between the Global North and South can't be overlooked. The paper highlights, through case studies and multilateral dialogue, the intricacies of creating cooperative solutions amidst a highly unequal global order.

Keywords: Geo-Strategic Relations, Global South, Multilateral Dialogues, Non-Traditional Threats,

Introduction

The end of Cold War marked not only the dominance of an ideology, as Francis Fukoyama remarked as the "End of History", but also limited the threats of war. The Bipolar world which gradually shifted towards Unipolarism started embracing the human-oriented threats. With the global turn of events including 9/11, Chernobyl disaster, opening of enclosed markets, and similar trends, the world started to juggle with delicate moves of balancing between regional interests and agendas to address nonconventional security threats. The common characteristics of these threats is that they are not confined to state-related agendas but often cross borders and governments. In the modern 21st century, ensuring the survival and dignity of human beings worldwide has remained the most befitting challenge.

Particularly, the late 1980s to 1990s dominant neoliberal ideologies as popularly known as “Thatcherism” and “Reaganism” have triggered this emerging shift. The Structural Adjustment Programmes (SAPs) as promoted in the third world countries has further intensified the drive towards privatization and introduced new international order. Such interesting global shifts have compelled to rethink the national and regional security structures. The need to reshape the security structure became imperative considering the “challenges to the survival and well-being of peoples and states that arise primarily out of non-military sources” as Prof Anthony have remarked. The non conventional threats including poverty, degrading environment, pandemics and human rights abuses has become a point of intervention by the actions and policies of Global institutions and the dominant Western States.

Research Objectives:

- To comprehend the deeper understanding of conventional and non-conventional security threats.
- To assess the matter of global inequity in relation to regional disparities.
- To highlight the global reality of lack of unified voice and disparities in interest within the greater Global south.

Research Methodology:

The research methodology for the undergone study is purely based on qualitative approaches. The developmental model of different regions are closely analyzed and as an appropriate method comparative technique has been chosen. The below study is based on secondary research of governmental reports, editorials, and discourse analysis of expert works.

Emerging Non-Traditional Security Challenges

The need for armed resources and ammunitions was a reality during the Cold War era with the rise of armed conflict and nuclear tensions. National security strictly was in the sense of defense, armed race, and formed alliances. But cold war ended with the possibility of turning the world into a global village where the focus shifted more towards human welfare.

The main campaigners of non-traditional threats are the non-state actors who looks after structural inequities. The dominant transnational issues in form of climate change, refugee influx , pandemics or rise of terror has came into international attention. States or regions have their unique response to attend these newly formed vulnerabilities and it results in patchwork global action.

Structural Disparities Amidst International Institutions

Global South economies are increasingly getting depended on the Global financial institutions. These financial institutions like the International Monetary Fund and World Bank was primarily

set up to ensure stability of world economy. But through instruments like Structural Adjustment Programmes (SAPs), the domestic economies are vulnerable to market hands. SAPs began with eliminating state subsidies from the notable sectors including education, health, and agriculture. Specially in case of India, 1990s onwards these various liberalized policies involved the withdraw of government from subsidized welfare programs. Small scale farmers were caught in debt and these increased the net rural poverty and annual farmer suicide rates. Financial insecurity due to maladjustment of Global institutions is an unavoidable part of non-traditional security.

These Bretton Woods Institutions are perpetuating inequality by imposing unequal policies and providing upper hand to the developed states over the developing states. The key positions of the institutional settings are controlled by Western nations and thereby erodes the integrity and sovereign policy of the member countries.

The Question of Sustainability and Global Inequities

Environmental risks are the most critical non-conventional security concerns. Lack of natural resources, natural disasters, pollution, and global warming mainly hit the Global South, even though these countries emit much less compared to industrial nations.

Environmental concerns are like the slow ticking bomb if not addressed today at the international forum then it would have devastating impacts. But the role of sustainable environmental actions are always a point of contestation. Global South Countries have raised their voice against industrial nations for maximum carbon emission. So, the international green policies should also take into account their reduced emission burden in the past and the need for a sustainable environmental developmental model. Particularly, the 2015 Paris Agreement agreed to do away with this by accepting the concept of “common but differentiated responsibilities”. However, the commitment to such differential goals again become doubtful with the walking away of USA from the Paris Agreement under the leadership of President Trump. Even though Biden Government rejoined the agreement but their commitment to these agreements is a time testing phenomenon.

Another example is the environmental resource scarcity such as the Water Wars. These should not only be considered as an environmental threat. The concept of environmental disparity becomes ever-widening in this case. Repeatedly a group of developing or least developed countries has asserted unequal distribution and utilization of ecological resources. However, regional forums and third world countries are lacking a common consolidated voice.

South-South cooperation has become a model to transcend such imbalances. South Asian, Southeast Asian, and African countries increasingly collaborate to implement sustainable development models in sync with their regional climate. However, these efforts continue to be under the weight of budgetary limitations as well as technological dependence on the West.

The North-South Tussle over Global Trades

The 1945 GATT (General Agreement on Trade and Tariffs) and its successor World Trade Organization, 1995 tried to institutionalize international trade rules. However, it further opened the battleground between the North and South regions. The developing countries often allege WTO as “White Men’s Institution” have Pro-Northern tilt. The rules and regulations particularly related to trade, intellectual property (TRIPs, TRIMs), agriculture are regarded as highly asymmetrical by nature.

The Southern block demands for reparative justice while the Northern side retaliates with the charges of human rights abuses. Particularly populated countries like India and China being exploiting laborers with stringent regulations, lesser pay and maximum working hours. Institutions like the International Labour Organization (ILO) is framing allegations about bonded and cheap labor in emerging economies like India and China. The New International Economic Order ((NIEO) since 1974 or at least emerging economies like India continuously tries to assert principles of noninterference of transnational or multinational organizations in National actions.

Such allegations and counter allegations are depicting unequal power dynamics and an environment of “mistrust” about the foundation and working of the international institutions.

The International Labour Organization (ILO) helps to mediate these tensions, particularly over labor rights. But the charges tend to get politicized, further straining North-South relations.

Terrorism and Constructed Security Narratives

An important aspect of nontraditional security threats largely considered is the growth of inter and intra-state terrorism. But the question of disparity among regional organizations is eminent because of the tendency of equalizing terrorism with Islamic extremism. Especially after the Arab Spring avalanche and the resurrection of the ISIS threat, the Islamophobic tendency among Western organizations like NATO or European nations has been doubted by the Middle East or particularly Islamic groups of States. Such OIC or the Organization of Islamic Countries sees them as colonial acts or biases towards oriental nations. These OPEC nations are adopting initiatives to end these Islamophobic tendencies.

Disparities Within Southern Regional Responses

Leaving aside the Global uniformity, regional responses to non-traditional security threats are rarely effective and coordinated. Within the larger South Asia or South-East Asia for instance, there are wide scale regional diversity in terms of economic, political and cultural demands and aspirations. So, given that their responses and priorities also shifts with conditions.

The umbrella term “developing countries” itself is a misfit when accommodating countries like China and India with Maldives and Bangladesh in the same frame. The tendency to lumping all of

them within the same category conceals their internal socio-economic, political conditions thereby escaping the reality.

World institutions aside, regional responses to non-conventional threats are seldom effective and coordinated. Regional diversity—economic, political, cultural—implies that there will be differences in responses and priorities.

Even though regional organizations like ASEAN, African Union, OPWC+ are trying to develop common frameworks for managing collective security challenges. However, due to political rivalries and weak institutional capacities, such policies have failed to show lasting commitments. Other organizations like SAARC in itself is dead with member countries like Pakistan and India having border and territorial rivalries. So, whether there's any common "Global South" agenda in itself is a point of contestation.

Conclusion:

The overarching task of managing non-conventional security threats in today's world politics is nothing less than major policy undertakings. The present security requirements are based on trans-border problems that are beyond hard and smart power weapons. The ultimate task is of meeting human well-being in terms of sustainability. Somewhere a balanced development approach has to be adopted to stop linear growth of the West. However, what is lagging is these uniform measures to meet the challenges. The primary reason has been the internal contradictions, economic imbalances, and ideological fault lines.

Basically a two fold strategy can help in addressing the world realities. Firstly, regional organizations need to develop there overall capacity to implement region specific solutions. Secondly restructuring of the major world institutions to open up the decision making power to the third world countries. Overall these non-conventional security challenges are interdependent which can only be addressed through inclusive participatory processes.

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